

The Transforming Face of Retailing in India: E-tailing

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Abstract

In India now E-commerce, Internet shopping and cyber malls (termed as e-tailing) are some of the topical approaches which have appealed to academicians and practitioners of marketing in recent times. There are few observations that remind us that E-commerce and E-tailing is a reality and not a myth. Certain product categories, such as books and music, are readily amenable to Internet shopping. Even FMCG products may be amenable to Internet shopping. Amazon.com, which deals in books and music software, is accessible to consumers around the world. Closer home, there is Fabmart and Rediff. Amul products are sold to a 50,000 strong customer base (in several cities) through the Net. B2B marketing is already experiencing the impact of the Internet. Electrolux has introduced a Web-based washing machine abroad. Hindustan Lever Ltd plans to use e-commerce to unlock an inventory worth Rs 1,400 crore, which is generally stocked by its 7,000 stockists and over a million retailers. It has 14 manufacturing locations. E-commerce will certainly change the way consumers, manufacturers, intermediaries and suppliers communicate with each other. But, with all these developments, marketers have to consider a few fundamental questions before they build brands on the Net or woo customers through the Net. In connection with the theme this paper focus on the current outlook of E-tailing in India, the essence of E-tailing, important growth drivers of E-tailing in India, growth barriers of E-tailing in India, some of the real issues in E-tailing, and the innermost touch points to focus on in E-tailing in India.

E-tailing in India

The Internet has emerged as a cost-effective way of doing business especially in the retail sector. Its impact is felt across retail services although the intensity of impact varies from service to service. There are various multidimensional framework classify retail services into distinct groups. Strategic characteristics of services, whether they are amenable to digitization also need to be discussed. The distinct evolved framework and illustrations help decide how the Internet can be effectively used in enhancing a retail business. According the P.K Sinha, entry of the Internet in the retail service business is an irreversible phenomenon. Use of the Internet as a tool for doing business in the retail sector will grow rapidly as such, and with the increasing contribution of the retail sector to the GDP of India.

The 21st century heralds the creation of new information and service-based businesses. These are a growing part of the digital economy. The E-tailing of services will assume a position of central importance in the future. Many attributes of the E-tailing of physical goods are directly transferable to selling services on the Internet.

The developments foreseen will massively reduce direct human interaction in the provision of retail services. In many areas, service without a face may at first take people aback. But, whether we like it or not, we are confronted with a "brave new world" of services (Zeithaml et al, 1996). Services require confidence, since they can only be described rather than experienced prior to being consumed. The Internet as an information medium is highly suitable for this, and will ultimately revolutionize much noticeably.

During the dotcom boom, E-commerce and E-tailing was the sunrise industry, the one that would change the face of the world. While Ebay and Amazon – the twin pillars of E-commerce in US did bring about paradigm shift in USA, the tech pundits in India are still a bit iffy about E-tailing in India. The E-commerce market was expected to touch 9210 Crore INR in 2007-08, E-tailing or RE-tailing market is only about 1150 Crore INR according to a survey conducted by Internet and Mobile Association of India and Indian Market Research Bureau (IMRB). For the purpose of this article E-tailing is defined as E-commerce sites including auction sites that sell groceries, apparel, CD's, books, electronic items, gifting item etc but exclude travel, digital downloads and online classifieds sites.

The top E-tailers in India are indiatimes.com, fabmart.com, rediffshopping.com. They have managed to retain their lead due to innovative business strategies, supply chain model and changing urban lifestyles E-tailing, or e-commerce can be described as transactions that are conducted over an electronic network, where the buyer and merchant are not at the same physical location, for example plastic card transactions via the internet. According to a recent study, presently there are 4 million Internet users in India and the number is growing by leaps and bounds. Computer hardware & software, cinema, books, music cassettes /CDs, travel tickets and gifts and cards are sold through the net in a big way.

E-tailing: The Quintessence

With the fast development of various e-business solutions companies seek for new opportunities to get in touch with customers and build new type relationships. If in planning everything looks pretty simple and straightforward, in reality there are a lot of issues that shall be considered prior to launching full scale implementation. E-tailing is exactly this kind of beast. It brings a lot of operational and financial benefits, but it needs to be tamed (Papers4you.com, 2006).

Retailing is frequently viewed as the integral part of the marketing mix strategy (Leny & Weitz, 1998), where "place" plays the role of the transactional environment (Underhill, 2000). With the development of e-commerce the companies from different goods and service industries decided to become closer to customers by opening e-stores and managing e-tailing. Various traditional players like Gap, Tesco, Asda, HP, Cisco and new ones like Amazon, E-Bay, Lastminute.com opened electronic stores to satisfy instantly the customer needs. Of course, there are numerous examples of the successful e-tailing operations. However, it is important to remember that not all of the entrants in e-commerce were that successful (Mahajan et al., 2002). The point is that e-tailing is not the scheme which is easy to implement. There are a number of aspects that shall be considered. For instance the importance of product physicality and the influence of other buyers on the purchase decision (Underhill, 2000). The great number of fashion related items or products that are connected with self-image concept require the possibility of trying the product and see the reaction of others. Without it the whole process of purchase lacks important chemistry which makes it so addictive.

The suitability of certain product line-up with e-tailing depends on the degree of the involvement which is necessary for the successful purchase decision. Certain products can be treated as trivial or unimportant as they required little involvement and do not incur significant costs in case of wrong purchase whereas other products are very individual specific and require the high level of involvement prior to purchasing.

The other important element of "place" is atmospherics. For instance, potential customers might omit certain goods and not even recognize the want for them unless they are influenced by a certain stimuli like the combination of odour, lighting, colour effects, music and other elements

of atmospherics. In case of e-tailing there shall be something that would compensate the absence of these elements. There may be great number of alternatives like door-to-door delivery, reduced prices, the recommendations of experts, price and quality comparative tables to name a few. What e-tailing concept shall definitely have is the bunch of value-added benefits which a customer would never get in a traditional retailing environment (Papers4you.com, 2006). To conclude this overview it is important to remember that e-tailing is not the extension of traditional retailing. It is new environment with its specific rules of engagement where customers perceive a lot of things differently from the way they would do in brick-and-mortar environment.

E-commerce and E-tailing, from a business perspective offer an opportunity to cater to consumers across geographies, no operational timings, unlimited shelf space – and all this with miniscule quantity of infrastructure. For a country like India, this business model is a good way of growing the consumption driven economy.

Growth Drivers of E-tailing in India

The growth in the E-tailing market is driven by the need to save time by urban India. Besides with over 2.8 billion internet users, access to internet has also played an important role in growing the markets. Changing demographics (youthful India), changing lifestyles and exposure to the developed markets sure give a boost to this fledgling industry. The soaring real estate costs in India have certainly inspired many an online venture. Also E-tailers have developed many innovative promotions to lure customers and there by growing the market. Here are some of the arguments for the growth of E-tailing in India.

Increase in the number of online buyers and sellers: The success of a virtual marketplace depends on the presence of a large number of buyers and a large number of sellers. Over the years there has been a sharp

increase (as shown in the given figure)¹ in the number of online buyers and sellers in this segment. In addition to online buyers, many offline stores have begun to sell their products in the online marketplace. The greater the number of sellers and buyers, the faster the market grows.

Change in the customer's attitude: There has been a significant change in the attitude of an average Internet user. Consumers are ready to experiment to suit his convenience. Truly, an average user is buying a variety of products online. These may vary from low-end items like books to high-end items like laptops; less involving items like flowers to high involvement items like jewelry.

Convenience: As it is very evident that , A 15 minutes trip online can save a two-hour trip to the mall...we offer widest variety, the best deals and option for buying and paying online that won't take more than 5-6 clicks. Thus, an online buyer saves time, effort and money when buying online as compared to buying from physical stores.

Better Bargains: E-tailing eliminates the need to maintain expensive and fancy showrooms. Instead, what attracts customer attention to online stores is the '*great deals*' '*best prices*' and '*better bargains*'. As per one of the article published in the Times of India in the first week of January, "*Online retailers can manage to offer attractive offers as they operate out of websites and thus save on inventory handling and maintenance costs*".

No real estate costs: E-tailers do not have to maintain expensive showrooms or warehouses in prime locations, they operate through their web sites and thus save drastically on the real estate costs. The real estate costs in the metropolitan cities are sky high. Besides this, maintenance costs of a virtual store vis-à-vis a physical store is much less.

Easy and comfortably: Easy and comfortably obtained info is another advantages that shopping on the net offers. On the Internet, product information is just a few clicks away, all accessed in the comfort of a home. Traditional retailing stands out in stark contrast: the consumer searches

¹ Source: Active Internet Users, I Cube 2006, Syndicated Research of Technology Group@IMRB, March 2006

frantically, runs up and down, and grills a poorly trained store assistant who is unable to help him out. In the bargain, valuable time is lost. Simply put, shopping on the Internet for, say 15 minutes could save a two-hour trip to the mall. Consumers prefer to save this time so that they can devote more time for their professional and domestic priorities.

Better interaction with the customers: The greatest benefits of online commerce is its ability to establish interaction en-masse. Interaction refers to the ability of reaching customers on an individual basis and react appropriately to responses of individual customers. Interaction is a vital tool for mass customization. Examples are many and include online marketing of flowers, software books and education. This has also led to greater satisfaction among the online buyers. According to a research agency, 82% of the online buyers have been found to be satisfied with their purchases.

Mass Media/Coverage: A supermarket has limited area of operation. It caters to customers of a city (and/or its suburbs), but a web site can be accessed from any part of the country or for that matter from any part of the world, thus increasing the potential customer base.

Growth Barriers of E-tailing in India

But then all is not well in the E-trailer's paradise. The cost of customer acquisition is pretty high in India – about 1100 INR/customer which eats into the margins, as most goods retailed are low value items such as books, CD's and electronic gadgets. High margin goods such as apparel are not very popular because of the touch and feel factor. Most Indian's are not comfortable using their credit cards for shopping and there is always a fear of "what you see may not be what you get". There may be a problem with complaint resolution, especially after receipt of wrong goods or delayed delivery.

Consumer Bias: As it appears to be very apparent from the industry environment, "Consumers will display a bias for brands that they know well and have had a good experience in the past". Thus products of brands with a favorable bias will score over the products of less popular brands. "A few would take risk to buy expensive jewelry from an unknown jeweler online", said by the

V. V. Rao while he discussed the case of Wal Mart at IIM, A during the 30th faculty development program.

Lack of ‘touch-feel-try’ experience: We have heard a lot of Internet Users say “would the diamonds in the ring be as big as shown in this picture”, “it seems like my size but what if does not fit well”, “what if this camera does not work”. Thus, lack of ability to try a product before buying acts as a barrier for some Internet Users. In addition, often the product or the service delivered differs from the standards displayed on the website. The customer is not sure of the quality of the product unless it is delivered to him and post delivery of the product, it is sometimes a lengthy process to get a faulty or the unsuitable product changed. Thus, unless the deliverables are as per the customers expectations, it is hard to infuse more credibility in the e-Tailing market.

Mounting competitive pressures: The market for online buying is still at a nascent stage. However, at this early stage too, the market is swarmed by the players selling their or third party’s products online. To attract customers, the competing online players are adopting all means to provide products and services at the lowest prices. This has resulted in making the consumers choice-spoilt, who in turn surf various websites to spot the lowest price for the product. Thus, although the number of transactions is increasing, the value of the products sold is continuously falling owing to high competition and leaner margins.

Seasonality: E-tailing Market is faced by seasonal fluctuations. August to February is the peak seasons for sale, while March to July is the dry seasons for sale. During the peak season, occasions that drive the sales are Diwali, Rakhi, Valentines Day, New Year, Christmas, Mother’s Day, Friendship Day etc are. On these occasions younger generations prefers buying and sending gifts online.

Credibility in payment system: It is also found that, “online frauds and breach is the biggest barrier to online sales”. As a result, prospective buyers prefer staying away from revealing their credit card and bank details.

Untimely Delivery of products: it might take a few minutes to search, book and pay for products and services online, but the delivery of the product may take unreasonable time. Thus, the online retailing raises more issues than the benefits it currently offers. The quality of products offered online and procedures for service delivery are yet to be standardized. Till the same is done, the buyer is at a higher risk of frauds. In addition to above, efforts need to be taken to educate the online buyers on the steps that need to be undertaken while making an online purchase. Moreover, the feedback of an online buyer should be captured to identify flaws in service delivery. This can be done through online communities and blogs that serve as advertising and marketing tools and a source of feedback for enterprises.

Thus, unless the issues surrounding the E-tailing market are addressed, the benefits provided by the industry would fail to attract high value and volumes of transactions.

E-tailing: The Real Issues

The Indian Retail industry has always thrived on personalization. The grocer, tailor or even the mom and pop shop, or apparel store owner knows the preferences, remembers customer's taste, budget and previous purchases. They sense the customer's mood too – which no CRM software can claim to do.

Trying to personalize each customer's experience – might be one way to grow. The Indian consumer is still very need oriented, not very impulse or deal oriented like the American counterparts or other developed nations. Hence it might make sense to create real consumer centric promotions constantly that provide real value to the Indian consumer. Slowly but surely this is happening in India.

There have been horror stories about receipt of bad or wrong goods, delayed deliveries, no response from the company – which adds up to not trusting the online retailers. Through this changing – albeit slowly, thanks to automation and technical integration.

Touch points to focus on

1. Customer is the King – A good 24/7 customer service through e-mail, chat and toll free phone is what the E-tailers are providing. Customer complaint resolution – whether, delayed delivery, product quality, wrong product delivered will certainly work towards long term customer relationship, retention and acquisition.

2. Supply Chain - Most customer complaints and delivery returns can be traced to the supply chain vendors or merchants. They are in fact the most important internal customers. It is important to have the supply chain vendors or merchants well integrated into the system – both technically and strategically.

3. New Business Models - E-tailers always search new and innovative business models. Case in point being US based Power Reviews – where it provides free review technology to E-tailers and all it asks in return is that the reviews collected on the retailer's web site are syndicated, which is then aggregated on the Buzzillions.com, its sister website. Some Indian sites simply collect orders over a period of time say a week, order in bulk from the vendor and finally ship it to customer at a discounted rate. The customer is told beforehand about the delivery date, of course.

4. Comparison Shopping and Customer Reviews - All the E-tailers are present on comparison shopping sites is of paramount importance – especially since people now visit these sites before they place the order. Being present on well known sites such as compareindia.com and wize.com is a very good idea. Also they encourage customer to write the product reviews – nothing authenticates their offering to an undecided customers like a good product review.

The Conclusion

Though much is yet to be achieved, remember E-tailing is a new-fangled industry in India. With broadband internet access still accessible to entire population, this industry may see an explosive growth. Most growth drivers are in India's favor – demographics, economy, changing lifestyle, exposure to new ideas. It is just a question of creating a sustainable eco system for E-tailing, which is at an inflection point. The coming Time to fasten the seat belts!

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